

Nisha as a Rebel in Manju Kapur's *Home*

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Manju Kapur is one of the most famous writers among the other contemporary Indian English writer. She clearly shows her academic experiences from her choice of, milieu, characters and plot. She sets everything is very perfect to develop mutual atmosphere with the public in everyday life. Through her works greatly analyze the human relationship under the roof of home or family. She gives more importance to the family relationship. Family is the basic in Indian society. She not only focuses the human relationship but also liberates her female characters from the repressive measures of patriarchal society. In her protagonists are underwent, physical, emotional, and psychological sufferings, but at last all of them to get their freedom at a considerable extent.

Kapur's *Home* is the exclusive tale of family and human relationship. Family is the root to develop religious thoughts, consensus, strong relationship and respect to each other. Family is the primary source of real happiness in human life and sequel of human existences. Home is considered as the place of Learning. Family explains us to realize human relationship which is the substance of the sequel of human survival. From the family, humans are learning the piousness, mutual understanding and respect to each other. It helps to the human to develop strong relationship. Family is regarded as the primary position and the authority of pleasure and learning.

In the modern age, the perception of home is scary state. Human relationships are also on the edge of transformation. Transformation has occupied all the places. The ancient customs and tradition the feelings of human relations and the family a reside-lined. Some of things occur in the name of modernization and some of things the sake of change. Transformation's effect is very terrible. Modernity affects the piousness of home and family. It also affects the emotions of people and it also the human attitude sentiment and sympathy. Money plays a vital role in the modern society. It also complicates the situation of family. It analyses everything on the basis of materialism. Modernization also commands the emotion and human sentiments. Indian novelists are take part in the debate. R.K. Narayan is one of the famous Indian English writers. In his novel she tries to bring out few barest facts of family life. Most of all Human relationship is the core

issue of his novels. He shows his deep insight in telling the story about home, and also, he is the expert of human psychology.

Home is the common story of every Indian home. This story covers nearly the four generation of people and their daily life. It deals Nisha's hopes, aspirations, failures and frustrations. It also deals with the conflict against ancient traditional rules. It portrays different type of human relationship in an attractive way. Kapur explores her profound insight of human nature and illustrate her mellowness as a novelist. Once again, she goes back to her old theme of three generations of people living in a house.

Woman in contemporary society has become aware of the fact that the inferior position accorded to them is not pre-ordained. Women are trying to emancipate themselves from subordination. Indian women keep on struggling against the burden of tradition, against the legacy of the past and the orthodoxy of patriarchal system" (2003:27). The protagonist of the novel, Nisha lives the life in the shackles of responsibilities. The novelist not only describes the plight of woman in the joint family, but also their sacrifices for the family.

Thus, it is a novel about the quest of identity of three women, especially Nisha, who struggles against the conventional and traditional rule of family. Her family is conventional and traditional. It never adopts the new idea and gives up the old one. Two sisters Rupa and Sona, have different opinions on the topics of education and career. Sona is a traditional woman who believes in the duty to the family. She is committed to her family. And this commitment is everything for her. Nisha's mother Sona considers marriage as the ultimate destination for her daughter. And she also wants her daughter to follow her. She believes in the False ideas like that people are suspicious of brides that are very educated. Rupa think that girls should be educated so that they can be individuals.

Rupa tells that her husband says that a good degree gives you some thing to fall back on your own feet. Rupa succeeds in convincing her to send Nisha to Durga Bai College. It was a girl's college and a nice place for a girl waiting to get married. Thus, Nisha is sent to the college not to get any new idea or pursue her studies but to pass her time till she gets married. Nisha is exposed to the outside world as she enters the college. In college she compares herself with her other classmates. She also wants to be like them. On her way to college, Nisha falls in love with a boy named Suresh. He is a student of near by Khalsa College of Engineering. After many meetings Nisha boldly wanders here and there; roaming on the university lawns with Suresh. With the apparent progress in the affair Nisha becomes self-assertive and this boldness in Nisha is reflected in her changed costumes. She tries to project herself as a modern or forward girl. She knows that her conventional family setup will not accept her modernity but still she decides to cut her hair. Kapur catches this sense of adaptability. Along with Suresh, Nisha goes to the beauty parlour, cut her hair in open style. She looks extremely charming and beautiful. Suresh also appreciates it. Symbolically, she becomes independent. Still, she is afraid of forthcoming consequences. She has worried how she faced her parents in home. It seems to be a sense of revolt for her.

She goes home in dilemma "It greeted her as she walked through the front door. Who gave you permission to cut your hair, suddenly you have become so independent, you decide things on your own, where did you find the money, the time, the beauty parlour, where did you find all these things?" (HO 149-150). Soon her family discovers Nisha's affair. She faces many difficulties. She is literally made a prisoner in her own house, even not allowed to go alone anywhere. Nisha refuses to follow the traditional arranged marriage. The novelist expresses how in Indian family that a girl has no right to take decision for herself. She has to sacrifice all her wishes for the sake of her family. Nisha feeds up with the loneliness, decides to engage herself in some work. Nisha begins to work in a near by play school.

Flavours of Literature

As it is not enough to pass her day she needs something more. She considers the possibility of doing other things in the world. She wants to open her own business in order to establish herself in terms of corporate life. Since she is the daughter of a businessman it was not difficult for her to go through the acid test of the business life. She thinks herself to be better than pooja: “She would be better than Pooja. She would not only be the daughter of a prosperous man but be responsible for wealth herself. After all, her father’s blood flowed in her, the of blood traders” (HO 286).

Thus, Nisha’s Creations has started by Nisha herself. She get twenty-five thousand from her father. She promises him to pay every rupee within time. She has learnt the graphs of the market carefully. She has managed the market with her full insight. She valued her credentials well. Nisha succeeded in her business. She understands the different shades of complications in the business. She pays half of the twenty-five thousand which she had taken to start the business. Gradually, she learns the value of life. Now, she is on her own feet: “She had paid half the twenty-five thousand loans. With your blessings, papaji, you will get the other half by next year, she laughed, almost recapturing the liveliness that had been hers in college” (HO 295).

The novel presents Manju Kapur’s understanding of human characters and her maturity as a novelist, “My own feeling is described me any way you like, as long as I am relevant, as long as I am read, I don’t really care.... cultural trends, gender relations, class equations, all of the mare seen brilliantly in the novel.” Says Manju Kapur. The novels appeal ohernotonly as a writer, but as a teacher as well. As a writer of new generation in an atmosphere of the nation’s socio-political flux, Kapur has recorded the truth in her fictive narrative with Zeal to change the Indian make perception.

Kapur’s Home remembers to the readers Elain Showalter’s first phase of the Feminine Phase. She is of the opinion that women need an economical freedom from the male chauvinistic society. They want to break the rules and come out their cage to fly over the sky. Women are having at alent to run a business, earn money and become an independent woman. They create their own identity and then they don’t want depend on men. They dispute their conservative beliefs which, they strongly consider, demote them to the secondary status in the society. Nisha become a rebel and fulfil her dreams in life.

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